

Public Policy and Sexuality Education for Youth with Disabilities: Impact on Sexual Behavior and Outcomes

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Abstract : This paper will examine the need for more aggressive public policies around bodily, reproductive and sexual health education for young people with disabilities in the United States. This paper will consider the policies around sexuality education for students in the United States and the recommendation for national standards around sexuality education. We will investigate the intersection of these policies and recommendations for students with disabilities and the Individuals with Disabilities Education Act (IDEA): what this means for students with disabilities' access to comprehensive sexuality education and how it affects their behaviors and outcomes.

Keywords : disability, sexuality, education, policy

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